

RANK-DENOTING VULTURE AND ITS VARIANTS

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Annotation. The article provides information on the question of the rank-expressing word of thunder and its variants.

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In Uzbek linguistics, degree-expressing words are divided into two types into what words they relate to. That is:

- 1) words denoting the degree of the meaning of confirmation;
- 2) words denoting the degree of the meaning of negation;

We will stop only about words that indicate the level of the meaning of confirmation. Words denoting the level of the meaning of affirmation also have their own types. Also, such a level is characterized by the fact that each of the words denoting is characterized by its own semantic-grammatical feature, variant, coloring, to what words it binds. With this in mind, we found it necessary to study words that indicate the degree of confirmation meaning in two ways.

Not only in Uzbek linguistics, but also in Turkology as a whole, affirmative words denoting the level of meaning have been distinguished into types from a point of view. But words denoting such a rank can be grouped into types with some of their properties. For example, in terms of whether rank-expressing words can only gain the meaning of the word to which they are connected, or represent the rank peak of the word meaning, in terms of stylistic coloring and what stylistic coloring; differ among themselves in terms of variability. This means that they can be classified into species with certain points of view.

Words that achieve the level of meaning the word they associate with intensifies the level of meaning of words of the noun category made of quality, fluency, verb and the same by gaining in different stages, and this gain is distinguished in terms of strength or weakness in relation to each other. Words with such a feature are as follows: incredibly, very, immodest, pure, one, one, excellent, many, how, absolutely.

For example: I took the night away from the village, "Töganbek replied," He has a thin face (Oybek). Then the work was very scary (A.Kadiri). The third Brigadier made a clean disgrace (G'.G'ulam). He made a scourge, he made a scourge. Even in my dream, if I do not get enough for you (from the newspaper "Tashkent evening").

All rank-signifying words in these examples have only gained and strengthened the meaning level of the word to which it is connected at different stages.

There are words that indicate a certain degree that, stylistically, acquire paint, acquire expressiveness, positive or negative character. Therefore, these types of rank-denoting words are further divided into two within themselves.

1. Expressive paint signifiers;
2. Subjective reactionaries;

The words of the first kind are, in principle, strange, pure, one, one, okay, big, infinite, absolutely, how much, rosa, obdon, etc.

These add a unique lift, each by wiping and reinforcing the level of meaning of the word to which it is connected. This means the expressiveness of the word of that rank.

One of the words denoting Rank is the word Thunder. It is also one of the degree-denoting words that it uses in a wide range. He, too, suffocates on adjectives, verbs, and noun derivatives, gaining and reinforcing to some extent the meaning of the word in which he is attached.

The intensification of the meaning of the word hyperbole is unique in that it has a lower expressive character compared to its very, clean words.

The term hyperlinks to words in the adjective or adverbial category meaning a character, and indicates their level of meaning by increasing their degree. For example, the people of Yaqubek had an extremely sincere vision with Navoi and presented gifts (Oybek). Ahmadjan, whose vision of war was different, valued everything that would become a building with Labor, was deeply affected by this landscape (A. Qahhor). In this place, too, the hyperbolic also exaggerated the power of their expressiveness by gaining the level of meaning of the intimate, hard words to which it is connected.

The term hyperlinks in meaning by exaggerating a perceived trait and vividly conveys stylistic content. For example, that person is a carefree person (Oybek). The old man of poppy will be the most stubborn of those in the category (G'. Ghulam). In such statements, the hyperbole reinforces the meaning of the word to which it is connected and expresses it through the positive attitude of the subject. Just like these, the word hyperbole, like the word juda, increases, lengthens and intensifies the meanings of the word it is connected to, time, distance, quantity, etc. The word hyperlink also has a very verbal-like property in this respect, but has little level-raising power compared to it.

Thus, the hyperbolic signifies character, trait, state by binding to words that convey meaning, reinforcing their level of meaning, and indicating it with expressiveness. When bound to words with the meaning of quantity, distance and time, it expresses its meaning by lengthening and multiplying it by a certain amount.

The verb stem attaches to the verb stem, and the meaning-conscious state increases the expressiveness by intensifying the action and exaggerating it. For example, the child was adored (G'. G'ulam). The Roadman who served among these noble people was overwhelmed (Oybek). In this case, the hyperbole was a passive action signifier, the state was attached to the expressions, reinforcing its level of meaning and exaggerating the power of influence of the compound.

The word thunder does not connect to horses that have a pure object meaning. But some horse made of the adjective category, which has kept the adjective mark, will become attached to the noun phrase and strengthen the meaning. For example, a chain reaction develops at an extreme rate (F. Vatur). In this position, the Vulture came with the word Tada, further exaggerating the meaning of the horse in the sense of the sign. In this case, the words very, very, extremely, finally do not apply instead of the proverb, but finally the word can be used.

Another characteristic feature of the word Thunder is its wide range of uses in a more classical style.

In the opening of the force of influence of a word or a compound, in the concrete expression of the color of meaning, several forms of the word hyperbole are used in ideation, tolerance, hyperbole. These also increase the level of meaning as opposed to the word of Thunder. For example, the streets were crowded (G'.G'ulam). He was afraid of the answer. It was said that the work was very delicate, frightening in the idea (A.Kadiri). In this sentence, the word "ghaytat" further exaggerated the meaning of the word "crowded", further reinforcing the meaning of the word "fear", and even adding additional meaning to the content of the sentence. Because there is a significant difference in the impressiveness of the meaning in the case when it is applied with the meaning in the case when the word is not used in the idea. Also Mirzahalim, humble (Oybek). Mountains with chains that shoulder to the clouds, wandering cockatiels, all this is incredibly beautiful. It was husnikhat, to whom the word of tolerance in these sentences is associated, who strengthened and increased the character level of his beautiful words. A distinctive feature of the word tolerance is its attachment to words with a positive meaning of paint. Another quote. For example, I was very angry that I was born a daughter from a mother (G'.G'ulam). In this position, the hyperbolic word strongly expresses the meaning of the compound to which it is connected, indicating the highest, strongest rank ottenka within variants of the hyperbolic word.

Thus, the word hyperlinks to adjectives, inflections, verbs, and noun derivatives, reinforcing and acquiring a sign, State, action perceived from the word. It is expressed by increasing and lengthening the meanings of quantity, time, and distance in syllables, such as the word "very". In gaiety as opposed to Gaiety, gag, gag forms express the level of meaning with a stronger and more influential ottenka. Its expressiveness will also exceed. This kind of variational rank expresses the meaning level of a word that is connected to itself by several different variants of its own by increasing and intensifying it at different stages. Words denoting such a variant rank are of great importance for the lively, touching and realistic expression of subjective assessment. It was this subjective assessment, the necessity of expressing the degree of meaning in different stages, that gave rise to the variants of the words that indicate the degree.

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